

**Information management: Education as a digital
organisation in the U.K**

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Overview

Electronic information management Systems of the universities in the United Kingdom are designed and developed to play a key role in automatic administrative work and learning. The current COVID-19 pandemic has changed the dynamics of operations globally. The education sector has witnessed a significant change in terms of administration and learning delivery since the beginning of lockdown. In the United Kingdom, each sector has tried to restructure the basic information management system and process to have well-configured systems that help mitigate the lockdown effects. Universities in the United Kingdom has explored various options to ensure the continuity of their electronic information management system with innovations and development. This has changed the mode of learning delivery and administration in those educational institutions.

Several educational delivery methods have been integrated, while new and efficient methods are being designed and developed to enhance learning with technology. Innovations associated with this adoption and trend have been continuous, and many awaits to be explored to contributes its quota to an efficient and continuous learning process during and after the COVID-19 era.

Objectives

The focus of this paper is to explore the various electronic information management systems applicable to the United Kingdom Universities, considering the digital mode of educational delivery, which could also be regarded as online learning. We need to understand how those new electronic information management systems and the processes work carefully, the benefits, limitations and how it could be improved; the role it's likely to play in coming years for proper learning and interaction helps get ready for the future.

Problem statement

The global community faced with the challenge of COVID-19 measures has contributed towards the rise in the adoption of technology to manage information and communication hence the digital revolution. These have led to a change in the administration and learning process in education. The U.K is one of the countries that have now become dependent on information management systems.

Education as the digital organisation

Some significant information management systems, including the documents management, records management, digital asset management, learning management systems, collaboration, etc., are all now being managed with the

aid of technology. All these systems dwell on the skills of the people involved, technological advancement, and content delivered. These systems have brought changes that now help manage learning at the universities without the need for physical contact. It has enhanced interaction between lecturers and students. It is now said to have a place for continuity post-corona virus pandemic period.

This pandemic period has served to be a leveller in a way for all stakeholders such as educators, learners, policymakers, and the society at large in all parts of the world regardless of the level of development. How each now copes and adopt a system to curtail the effect depends on an understanding of their system, vulnerabilities, and shortcomings. The U.K educational system, which is long overdue for change, has now welcome a rebirth of the new system and innovations.

The world of social distancing has fostered greater digitalization of services and communication. This may soon become the norm in our daily lives and services. Most advanced countries with more people with digital literacy. They adopt better compared to those in the developing world. Policymakers have created and implement policies in favour of people with fewer privileges or digital literacy with access to affordable devices to help their learning during this period.

Methods of delivery

Learning delivery with technology is not a new concept in the U.K. However, some innovations have been integrated, creating an advanced electronic information management system. The new electronic information, such as virtual conferences and learning, use of live classrooms via zooms has helped in improving the interactions which occur between instructors and students to foster learning. An essential change to the system dynamics is evident in the lecture deliveries, learning, practical sessions, and assessments. The common delivery methods are those via various online platforms, dashboards, or emails.

Technology is gradually changing that historical, conservative educational model that focuses on one-one interactions between the lecturers and students in the U.K Universities, which is known for centuries to be resistant to change.

Technology has now driven that long-awaited change from the old method of delivery dominated with blackboard and chalks to the new method where each student with a single finger-click can gain from the vast knowledge of Google rather than what an individual teacher can deliver at a session (Damian, 2019).

That change has now turned the computer screen into classrooms.

This modification to the electronic information management system in the U.K universities has transformed the system and services. U.K Universities already have internet platforms for submitting assignments, group works, support, and communicate with their respective instructors. Those platforms, in many

instances, have a database of educational materials students can download to learn. However, not many of the institutions consider investment in this line as a priority until the onset of lockdown.

Virtual teaching and learning: have now changed the mode of interaction (Damian, 2019). Sessions that can't be done virtually are now redesigned to consider various COVID-19 preventive measures outlined by the NHS. Various activities have come into play to ensure effectiveness and better delivery in achieving the goal of high quality and continuous educational delivery to the students during this pandemic period. These changes and acceptance of the technology are simply because we all live in a technologically-immersed world. Technology has become part of our daily lives.

3D virtual concepts: Practical contents have been delivered by different methods, such as the use of 3D virtual concepts. The 3D virtual concepts are now being adopted for courses that need practical or clinical sessions to be completed. Lecturers have soon quickly adopted the system and moved their teaching materials online while learning better technological dependent methods of student's evaluation and assessments.

Electronic information Management of the learning delivery methods

Digital platforms; U.K schools now utilize Zoom, Microsoft teams, Google classrooms to deliver lectures. Students could interact without barriers with their colleagues and teachers (Tazia Statucki, 2020). The process enhances

online learning. Provisions have been made in favour of the 'disadvantage students' to have access to laptops to learn online. Long journeys to school by some students have been removed (Tazia Statucki, 2020). They can learn from the comfort of their homes. Teachers have opportunities to reach out to students easily (Damian, 2019).

Infrastructure: Computers and the internet remain the infrastructure needed to achieve the goal because they could result in barriers that will limit the realization of the goals (Paul, 2020). There is a need to ensure this modality not just stop after the pandemic period but continues with a more and advanced infrastructure, curriculum modification, and many other areas that might need an upgrade to enhance learning. This remains the future of education in the United Kingdom.

Current status and roadmap for the future: Some Universities run a virtual café that gives students access to group study. Live-streamed lectures become the norm during this period. Private Universities have begun to develop their roadmaps for getting out of lockdown. Some universities, such as Cambridge, have sort of offering all its courses online for the 2020/21 academic year. Some universities in the U.K plan on having a mix of online lectures with small group teaching when a lockdown is fully eased, especially for their seminars, practical, laboratory, and supervision, which they feel will need to be held on campus.

Studies areas and cafeterias are being redesigned to meet the NHS guidelines for social distancing.

Services utilised during COVID-19 pandemic

Lockdown and quarantines have no ending dates in view, so as the digitisation of education, which has come to stay. EdTech is at the forefront of the change and adaptation during this COVID-19 pandemic in the U.K (Marnix, 2020).

Students are happy to adopt it because of its flexibility. Educational institutions in the country have adopted EdTech to support the teaching and management processes (Marnix, 2020). This model includes hardware, digital resources, software, and services. These help in the process of running the education institutions because it aids teaching, meet specific needs, and help the process of electronic information management in terms of information sharing and communication. Bolton College makes use of IBM Watson based virtual assistant, which is available to both staff and students (Marnix, 2020). These respond to an on-demand request for information that could be related to students, curriculum, or activities such as attendance or staff on administration activities and out-of-hours teaching. The University of Wolverhampton makes use of a 3D visualisation system to help manage the absence of traditional laboratory-based lessons on anatomy or dissection (Marnix, 2020). With touch screens, the system has increased student's participation and explore complex body relationships.

Innovations in databases and information management in the U.K. Universities are as important as their management. Educational institutes with innovation in database and information management systems have tapped into several benefits by appropriately managing it (Ågerfalk et al., 2020). Significant benefit those databases related innovation in universities brought to the sector include; reduced costs, saves time for operational work, enhance online course enrolment, and delivery for students. The databases and information management innovations have also enhanced various payment methods online, improve the educational experiences in the management of all courses, students, teachers, and resources (Ågerfalk et al., 2020). The innovations have had a great impact on improving communication among stakeholders utilising emailing, chat portals, video conferencing portals, and messaging systems. It has also helped provide the needed student's academic progress, institutes resources, and assets during this COVID-19 pandemic period.

The current and potentials changes this information management brought to university institutions in the United Kingdom

The current technology adoption for educational continuity at this pandemic period has fostered efficient administration where student's academic progress, institutes resources can be effectively managed. Earlier before the pandemic, most school electronic information management systems utilised by the U.K universities are focused on providing a platform where students can submit

coursework or assignments, interact with colleagues on discussion topics, or contact the instructors. There is no room for virtual educational delivery. Many of the schools have utilised various applications such as Zoom, Microsoft teams, Google classrooms to lecture their students and interact with one to replace the one-one mode of delivery universities are already adapted.

Preparation for full adoption in the future

At this time, many U.K universities now focus on ensuring improved educational experience while managing the online courses, students, teachers, and resources. This is achievable by many as an automated process for students and teachers timetables to avoid overlaps. The system encourages an effective system for the student because they have accessibility to lesson plans, which can guide their preparation for the class. They are also able to ask questions from colleagues via the student's portal.

Virtual forms of learning have come to stay. No ending date for a pandemic is available already; impending lockdown depends on the rate of cases recorded. Some U.K schools have adopted this mode of learning and educational delivery as the right method to complete the current or next session. Some have indicated their interest in creating a stable structure that will be continuous and used in the future to enhance learning. The structure has been associated by researchers to have many benefits to both the lecturers and students compared to the traditional mode of educational delivery.

The structure will make administration much comfortable than ever with regards to grading students and maintaining payrolls of the staff. The automated process now in place will continuously be researched for better efficiency. It gives room for more research in the field of information management, which will be based on the current understanding of operations. The overall educational experience of the Universities as a digitalised organisation will be based on the 'school management system' platform that will address the challenges identified after exploring the shortcomings of the current system and its inefficiencies over time. Planning to adopt the system for the future, it is important to understand different aspects. We understand that according to Leontiev, human activities are units of life which are thus organised into the three hierarchical layers (Hasan & Kazlauskas, 2014).

Conclusion

There is a top layer that represents the activity itself in this digitalisation system. This top layer is oriented towards the motive, which in this study is the need for continuous education delivery. This motive remains the object that the subject ultimately needs to attain. Actions taken in this content of organisational digitisation in the educational sector are conscious processes that are directed at the goals and must be undertaken by the stakeholders to fulfil the object with consideration to the targets. These actions are instituted via the lower-level units of activities called the operations. All these three-layered systems open up the

possibility to further study the system of educational delivery by analysing the motivations, goal-directed and operational aspects of the system. This will also help to bring up the issues of Why, What, and How within a consistent conceptual framework. The activity theory will thus be used as a lens in further analysing and understanding the processes and possible outcomes of the education as a digitalised organisation now and in the future.

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